

Voltammetry of Malathion

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Voltammetric studies of the reduction of malathion has been carried out in the pH range 1.5 – 12.5 in ethanol – water mixtures. Differential pulse polarography is used to develop an analytical method for its determination in trace levels. The electrochemical reduction mechanism is given in consistent with the data obtained. The kinetic parameters are evaluated and reported.

THE organophosphorous insecticide, *O,O*-dimethyl *S*-(1,2-dicarboethoxyethyl)dithiophosphate known as malathion is used widely in agriculture for controlling a wide range of important pests. For residue analysis Visweswariah and Jayaram¹ proposed a colorimetric method for the estimation of malathion. Clark and Qazi² modified and improved^{3,4} the recommended colorimetric method for the determination of malathion. Other methods for the detection and determination of malathion are reported in the literature^{5,6}. Apart from these, electrochemical methods⁷ can be used with an advantage of determining malathion in crude and residue samples.

The present study has been taken up to investigate the reduction mechanism of malathion and its estimation employing electrochemical methods such as cyclic voltammetry, d.c. polarography, a.c. polarography and differential pulse polarography in aqueous media. These electrochemical methods are based on the determination of stable breakdown product, i.e. fumaric acid which is obtained by the hydrolysis of malathion⁸ and not on the determination of *O,O*-dimethylester of phosphorodithioic acid which is unstable and undergoes decomposition in basic media.

Experimental

Malathion was supplied by Cyanamid India Limited, Bombay. The purity of the sample was tested by tlc. AnalaR grade samples were used for preparing the supporting electrolytes in double-distilled water. Malathion being polarographically inactive was determined by indirect methods such as hydrolysis. In hydrolysis (Scheme 1), malathion (1) rapidly and quantitatively breaks down to the sodium salt of the *O,O*-dimethylester of phosphorodithioic acid (2) and disodium fumarate (3) by a base-catalysed elimination reaction⁸. On acidification of the above, fumaric acid (4) which is polarographically active is obtained.

Scheme 1

D.C. polarograms were recorded on a PARC 364 polarographic analyser coupled with Kipp and Zonen recorder. A dropping mercury electrode of flow rate 2.73 mg s⁻¹ was used as working electrode and a saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode. A Metrohm E 506 polarecord connected with a E 612 VA-scanner was used for a.c. polarography and differential pulse polarography. A digital electronics 2000 X-Y/t recorder connected to Metrohm E 506 was used for recording cyclic voltammograms. The hanging mercury drop electrode of area 0.4437 cm² was used as working electrode in cyclic voltammetry and dropping mercury electrode of area 0.0224 cm² as working electrode in a.c. and differential pulse polarography. Ag/AgCl (s), Cl⁻ was used as reference electrode. All pH measurements were made using an Elico digital pH meter. All the polarograms were recorded after deaeration of the test solution with purified nitrogen at 26 ± 1°.

Results and Discussion

After hydrolysis, only one wave/peak has been observed for malathion in d.c. polarography, a.c.

polarography, differential pulse polarography and cyclic voltammetry in all the buffers except in the buffer of pH 6.85. This wave/peak corresponds to the reduction of fumaric acid which is obtained by the hydrolysis of malathion. The reduction product was confirmed by spot test⁴ as succinic acid. But in the case of pH 6.85, two waves/peaks were observed at -1.06, -1.18V at -1.12, -1.29V as shown in Figs. 1 and 2 in 10% ethanol which correspond to the reduction of fumaric acid to succinic acid in two-step process. In the first step a radical

Fig. 1. Typical d.c. polarogram of malathion in phosphate buffer of pH 6.85; concn.=0.4 mM, solvent=10% EtOH, drop time=8 s.

Fig. 2. Typical cyclic voltammogram of malathion in phosphate buffer of pH 6.85; concn.=0.4 mM, solvent=10% EtOH, sweep rate=8.

intermediate is formed. In cyclic voltammetry, a sharp cathodic peak has been observed nearly at -0.41V (Fig. 2) before the reduction of electro-active species. This peak observed in all the media has been found to possess the following properties

because of which it is characterised as adsorption peak⁵. At low sweep rates, the diffusion peak is predominant. As the scan rate is increased, the adsorption peak appears and increases with only a small decrease in the diffusion peak current function. With further increase of the scan rate, the adsorption peak current function increases further, and the diffusion peak current function decreases until only one peak appears at the potential of the adsorption peak. Appearance of this characteristic peak may be attributed to the strong adsorption of the hydrolytic decomposition product

of malathion, having a group $\begin{matrix} \parallel \\ -P-SH \\ | \end{matrix}$, which acts as a surface active substance^{1,6}.

Conventional log plot analysis, variation of $E_{1/2}$ and E_p values towards more negative potentials with increase in concentration of the depolariser show that the electrode process related to the reduction of fumaric acid to succinic acid is irreversible. The reduction processes are found to be diffusion-controlled as evidenced from the linear plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$ and i_d vs C .

The number of electrons involved in the electrode process is found to be two from the results of millicoulometry in all the buffers. The product was isolated as succinic acid by spot test from controlled potential electrolysis in acetate buffer of pH 4.0. The number of protons involved in the reduction of fumaric acid is evaluated as two from the plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH and E_p vs pH.

Reduction mechanism :

(i) Acid and basic medium :

(ii) Neutral reduction :

The possibility of adsorption of hydrolytic decomposition product, i.e. surface active substance as evidenced from a.c. polarographic and cyclic voltammetric measurements is likely to be the reason for low diffusion coefficient values noticed in these techniques (Table 1). The rate constants are observed in all the techniques except in a.c. polarography to be very low in the buffer of pH 6.85 indicating that the rate of reaction is slow in this medium when compared to acidic and basic media, since in this medium the breaking of π -bond is very difficult and also the formation of free radical is slow. The abnormal behaviour of rate constants ($k_{t,h}^0$) from the a.c. polarographic measurements is

TABLE 1—TYPICAL ELECTRODE KINETIC DATA FOR MALATHION

Concn.=0.4 mM, Drop time=3 s, 10% Ethanol, scan rate=40 mV s⁻¹

Supporting electrolyte	D.c. polarography		Cyclic voltammetry		A.c. polarography		Differential pulse polarography	
	D $\times 10^5$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	$k_{r,h}^0$ cm s^{-1}	D $\times 10^6$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	$k_{r,h}^0$ cm s^{-1}	D $\times 10^7$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	k_s $\times 10^{-4}$ cm s^{-1}	D $\times 10^7$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	$k_{r,h}^0$ cm s^{-1}
Clarks and Lubs buffer (pH 1.50)	1.85	9.13×10^{-11}	1.82	1.92×10^{-14}	1.63	1.72	2.33	2.49×10^{-11}
Acetate buffer (pH 4.0)	2.36	3.82×10^{-11}	1.90	3.96×10^{-16}	2.27	2.04	2.43	3.18×10^{-11}
Phosphate buffer (pH 6.85)	0.78	3.40×10^{-15}	3.22	9.53×10^{-14}	2.78	2.26	4.22	1.50×10^{-10}
Mollvaine buffer (pH 8.50)	2.45	1.25×10^{-15}	4.22	1.50×10^{-17}	2.94	2.28	4.46	1.93×10^{-14}
Carbonate buffer (pH 10.0)	2.89	7.87×10^{-16}	4.86	8.93×10^{-17}	3.16	2.76	5.54	4.19×10^{-14}

due to the magnitude and nature of the charge transfer contribution to the frequency. The decrease in rate constants with increasing pH may be attributed to the non-availability of protons.

Analysis: In the present investigation, d.c. polarography, and differential pulse polarography have been used for the quantitative estimation of malathion. Detection limit for d.c. polarography in the present investigation is seen to be $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$. With differential pulse polarography when compared to d.c. polarography, it is observed that the determination of malathion could be carried out even down to $1.0 \times 10^{-6} M$ levels. Since differential pulse polarography should improve sensitivity and resolution at still lower concentrations.

Recommended procedure (DPP): To the sample malathion (3.0 ml) was added 0.1 N NaOH (25 ml). After a hydrolysis time of 5 min, the contents were acidified with 3N HCl (10 ml) and diluted to 100 ml with double-distilled water to get a $4.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ standard solution. A carbonate buffer of pH 10.0 was found to be suitable medium for the determination of malathion. The standard solution (1 ml) was then placed in a polarographic cell and made up with carbonate buffer (9 ml) of pH 10.0 to get a concentration of $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ and then deaerated

with nitrogen. After recording blank polarogram, small increments (i.e. 1 ml of standard solution) were added and polarograms were taken. The optimum conditions for the analytical determination of malathion was found to be a drop time of 2 s and a pulse amplitude of 60 mV. The relative standard deviation was found to be 1.92%. The correlation coefficient was seen to be 0.962 in this method

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